

TEACHING THE TOPIC "PHYSICS OF THE SUN" AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *The given article discusses the integrative approach in teaching the topic "Physics of the Sun" studied on the subjects "Natural Sciences", "Physics", "Astronomy" in secondary schools. The methodological possibilities of the integrative approach in improving the quality and effectiveness of education are also methodically substantiated.*

Keywords: *general education schools, astrophysics, astronomy, solar structure, natural sciences, stars and planets.*

INTRODUCTION

It is important to suggest that at present time in our country, at the level of state policy much attention is paid to the issue of radical reform of the quality of teaching physics, which is the main tool of science and technology, and the development of society, the consistent application of innovative pedagogical technologies in the pedagogical process. This can be clearly seen only in the adoption of the Presidential Resolution PR-5052 of March 19, 2021 "On measures to improve the quality of education in the field of physics and the development of scientific research". Integration is the restoration of educational processes, the state of connecting individual parts and functions of the system into a single whole, as well as the process leading to this, that is, educational integration in astronomy teaching can be interpreted in different ways. The concept of "integration" in astronomy teaching has two meanings - as the goal of astronomy teaching and as a means of teaching.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

It should be mentioned that in this situation, each physicist-astronomer-teacher, in addition to mastering the fundamental knowledge of his science, must know the concepts, laws and principles of new fields and sciences that have arisen as a result of the mutual integration of sciences, and use this knowledge directly in the educational process, one must be able to use them. In particular, mastering the knowledge of the science of "Astrophysics" as a result of applying the laws, methods and principles of physics to astronomy, as well as mastering the results of experimental observations of the "Sun" and the theory of the nature of the physical processes occurring in it and their use in the processes of teaching physics is of great importance in the formation of the scientific worldview of students. This in itself expands the possibilities of effective integration of science and education. Since the science of "Astrophysics" was created as a result of interdisciplinary integration, therefore it is the most correct way from a scientific and methodological point of view to convey to students the nature of this integrative nature in the process of teaching physics. Although knowledge related to astrophysics is not specifically studied in school physics, knowledge about the structure of the Sun, the physical processes occurring in

it, and the impact of these processes on the Earth was obtained as a result of astrophysical research. In fact, knowledge of the "physics of the Sun" forms the basis of astrophysical knowledge in physics taught in the general secondary education system.

However, our pedagogical observations and analysis of existing literature on physics and astronomy for comprehensive schools show that today students' knowledge of astrophysics cannot meet modern educational requirements. However, students' interest in astronomy and astrophysics is actually very high. Therefore, an urgent task is to develop effective forms, methods and means of using these interests of students to improve the quality of education in practice.

The following factors also lead to the above problems:

Firstly, the lack of hours allocated to physics in comprehensive schools;

Secondly, insufficient attention is paid to the integration of knowledge of astrophysics into the physics literature created for secondary schools;

Thirdly, the subject "Astronomy", reflecting some aspects of astrophysics, is taught only in the 11th grade. And this does not allow for sufficient coverage of knowledge of astrophysics;

Fourthly, physics teachers in comprehensive schools lack modern knowledge of astrophysics, etc.

DISCUSSION

In this article, we present methodological recommendations for teaching knowledge on "Physics of the Sun" based on an integrative approach in a comprehensive school. The topic "Stars and Planets" of the textbook "Natural Science" for comprehensive schools presents general concepts about the Sun, which is considered the closest star to the Earth, as well as the simplest ideas about the differences between planets and stars, and students are given a mirror, with the help of which a practical task on the reflection of sunlight is determined. This is one of the simplest astrophysical experiments. Since a mirror is a physical device, and the Sun is an astronomical illuminator, then by changing the direction of light with the help of a mirror, it is possible to demonstrate the law of light return. In this simple experiment, to a certain extent, knowledge of several sciences (physics, astronomy, chemistry) acquires an integrative character, and the science of astrophysics shows their integration [1]. Topic 37 of the textbook "Natural Science" for the 6th grade of a comprehensive school is called "Stars", it provides information about the Sun, and explains that the Sun is not a planet, it is a star that emits light and heat from the information itself about the influence of the Sun on the nature of the Earth's surface, its atmosphere, flora and fauna, and human life. Although information is given about the water cycle in nature under the influence of sunlight, about the process of photosynthesis in plants, and that solar energy is widely used to generate electricity, its essence is not sufficiently disclosed [3]. In our opinion, in such a situation, the natural science teacher should more broadly disclose the essence of this concept and explain to students using real examples how electricity is obtained from the Sun, that a solar power plant has been built in Navoi region, and that the energy obtained here is used by residents of the region and in production. That is, solar energy is an environmentally friendly type of energy, people should understand that it does not have a harmful effect on their health, and they should understand the effectiveness of using this type of energy in practice. The 16th topic of the textbook "Natural Science" for the 3rd grade of comprehensive school is called "Stars", in which at first the Sun is the closest star to us, and in comparison, with other stars, not the largest, but the closest star to us. It is noted that due to its proximity to us, we receive enough heat and light from it, and its light reaches more than 8 minutes [2]. In addition, it is reported that the reserve of the Sun will not

suddenly fade away within a few billion years. In our opinion, when explaining this topic, countless stars in the sky emit light and energy, like our Sun, and this energy does not reach us due to the distance to the stars, and these stars are also divided into classes depending on their size and color.

CONCLUSION.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the effective use of the integrative approach in teaching astrophysical knowledge on "Physics of the Sun" in high school is of great importance in developing students' integrative thinking skills. This requires increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical research to expand the scope of use of the integrative approach in the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. Suyarov K.T., Tillaeva Z.Yu., etc. Natural Sciences. - T.: Gafur Gulam, 2021. -120 p.
2. Malikova V.Yu., Natural Sciences Grade 3. - T.: Novda Edutainment, 2023. -117 p.
3. Suyarov K.T., et al. Natural Sciences Grade 6 - T.: Republican Educational Center 2022. -190 p.
4. Satorov A.R. Teaching knowledge on "Physics of the Sun" based on an integrative approach in comprehensive schools. - T.: Science and Innovations. 2022. N. 3
5. Satorov A.R., Methodological manual "Modern Solar Physics", Tashkent, Sano-Stadart Publishing House, 2011. - 64 p.